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A Robust Hybrid DWT-DCT and Up-sampling Approach for Multiple Image Hiding

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ABSTRACT

The task of multi-image hiding involves embedding several confidential images within a single cover image such that the camouflage-image remains visually indistinguishable from the original, and all confidential images can be perfectly reconstructed. In this paper, we propose a novel hybrid image steganography method that combines DWT-DCT-based preprocessing and a high-ratio up-sampling mechanism with a spatial-domain reversible embedding scheme. First, a dummy embedding is performed using the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) and Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) on the interpolated pixels of an 8x up-sampled cover image. This step acts as a visual smoothing mechanism to improve the fidelity of the embedding surface while maintaining PSNR $\approx \infty$. Then, the actual embedding of multiple confidential images is performed using a block-based reversible data steganography method with Euclidean distance-guided block matching and pixel-level transformation. This combined approach ensures high steganography capacity, strong robustness, and perfect reconstruction of all confidential images. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed method outperforms traditional image steganography schemes in terms of visual quality, imperceptibility, and reversibility, making it suitable for secure multimedia communication and sensitive data storage.

Keywords - Image steganography, up-sampling, DWT-DCT transformation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The objective of image hiding, also known as image steganography, is to create a camouflage image by concealing secret information within a cover image. The hidden content can only be reconstructed by authorized receivers, while remaining imperceptible to others [1]. In comparison to conventional image cryptography techniques [2][4], image hiding offers a significant advantage in invisibility [5], and primarily focuses on four key factors: hiding capacity, camouflage-image visual fidelity, reconstructed image quality, and resilience against image processing attacks.

Traditional steganographic techniques mostly embed a single confidential image into a cover image [6][13]. However, the exponential growth in visual data transmission has made multiple-image hiding an increasingly critical requirement. Embedding several confidential images within one cover poses challenges in maintaining visual quality, ensuring perfect reconstruction, and resisting detection, especially when the payload size is large.

To address these challenges, various transform-domain and spatial-domain methods have been proposed. Recent hybrid approaches exploit the benefits of multi-domain embedding, particularly using Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) and Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT), which allow data to be hidden in high-frequency coefficients with minimal visual impact [2], [3]. Despite their robustness, many transform-domain methods require additional preprocessing or are limited by irreversible embedding and high computational cost.

On the other hand, up-sampling-based image hiding techniques offer a spatial-domain alternative with promising results. For example, Ping et al. [1] introduced an innovative RDH scheme in which the cover image is up-sampled and divided into non-overlapping blocks. Secret blocks

are embedded via block matching using Euclidean distance, followed by reversible intensity transformations. This method supports high hiding capacity, strong visual consistency, and perfect recovery of confidential images, even in RGB format. While the up-sampling-based approach provides excellent embedding capacity and reversibility, the interpolation process often introduces artifacts in the cover's interpolated regions. These can degrade block matching performance and slightly affect the camouflage image's smoothness. To overcome this, we introduce a hybrid enhancement step prior to the actual embedding phase.

In this paper, we propose a novel two-stage image hiding framework that combines:

1. A DWT-DCT-based preprocessing step performed exclusively on interpolated pixels of a 2x up-sampled cover image. A dummy secret is embedded in a reversible fashion—accepted only when the pixel-wise reconstruction of a block is exact ($\text{PSNR} = \infty$). This preprocessing acts as a visual smoother and prepares the cover for high-quality embedding.
2. A spatial-domain reversible data hiding method adapted from the existing IH-US technique [1], where the cover is further up-sampled to 4x and multiple confidential images are embedded using Euclidean-distance-guided block matching and reversible pixel transformations.
3. The proposed approach leverages the advantages of both frequency-domain refinement and spatial-domain capacity expansion. Experimental evaluations show that the camouflage images generated are visually indistinguishable from the original cover and that all confidential images are recovered without loss

- We introduce a DWT-DCT-based dummy embedding preprocessing technique applied only to interpolated regions of a 2x up-sampled cover, ensuring perfect reversibility and improved block smoothness.
- We employ a 4x up-sampling ratio in the main embedding phase to maximize capacity while preserving camouflage image imperceptibility.
- We integrate this preprocessing with a block-matching-based spatial embedding scheme capable of hiding multiple confidential images with perfect recovery.
- Extensive experiments validate the method's performance across visual quality (PSNR $\approx \infty$), robustness, and reconstruction accuracy.

II. RELATED WORK

Image hiding, or steganography, aims to embed secret information within a cover image such that the presence of the hidden data remains visually undetectable. Unlike encryption, which merely obscures the message content, steganography conceals the existence of the message itself, offering an added layer of privacy and security [1]. While many traditional approaches focus on hiding a single image [6][8], the growing demand for large-scale secure communication has led to the development of techniques that support the hiding of multiple images within a single cover.

A. Up-sampling-Based Multiple Image Hiding (IH-US)

One of the most effective techniques for reversible multi-image embedding is the interpolation-based Hiding via Up-sampling (IH-US) method, proposed by Ping et al. [1]. This method increases the embedding capacity by up-sampling the

cover image to expand the number of available pixels and block positions.

In this framework, both the up-sampled cover and the mosaic-combined confidential image are divided into equal-sized non-overlapping blocks each secret block is matched to a similar cover block using Euclidean distance computed from mean and standard deviation features. Once matched, reversible transformations (including intensity shifting and block rotation) are applied to embed the secret block. The process ensures:

- High camouflage image fidelity,
- Reversibility of the embedding process, and
- Perfect recovery of both cover and confidential images.

This IH-US technique forms the core of our embedding phase.

B. Proposed Enhancement: DWT-DCT Based Preprocessing

While the IH-US framework offers high capacity and lossless embedding, it can suffer from minor artifacts introduced by up-sampling interpolation, particularly in regions where block matching becomes ambiguous.

To overcome this, we propose a preprocessing step using a hybrid DWT-DCT embedding scheme on the interpolated pixels of a 2x up-sampled cover image. The technique selectively embeds a dummy secret into each 8x8 block using DWT followed by DCT applied to the HH sub band. A mid-frequency DCT coefficient (e.g., $C(5,5)$) is modified using:

$$C(5,5) \leftarrow 2 \cdot \frac{1^{(5.5)}}{2} + b$$

The inverse DCT and DWT are applied, and the modification is accepted only if the reconstructed block matches the original pixel-wise. This ensures the preprocessing

is lossless (PSNR = ∞) while improving the surface smoothness of the cover image, leading to more accurate block matching in the subsequent IH-US stage.

Fig 1. Workflow of DWT-DCT embedding

Algorithm 1: Image Hiding Using DWT-DCT embedding

Algorithm 1: DWT-DCT-Based Embedding into Interpolated Pixels

Input: A cover image C of size $M \times N$, and a confidential image S of size $m \times n$.

Output: Camouflage-image C' of $2M \times 2N$

1. Up-sample the cover image C by a factor of 2 using bilinear interpolation, filling values only in interpolated positions.

2. Convert the confidential image S into a binary sequence B of length $8 \times m \times n$.

3. Divide each color channel of the up-sampled cover image into non-overlapping 8×8 blocks.

4. For each interpolated 8×8 block (i.e., blocks where at least one of the top-left coordinates is even):

a. Apply 2D Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) using the Haar wavelet to obtain sub-bands LL, LH, HL, HH.

b. Apply 2D Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) on the HH sub-band.

c. Embed one bit from B into a mid-frequency DCT coefficient (e.g., position (5,5)) by modifying its LSB.

d. Reconstruct the HH sub-band using inverse DCT.

e. Apply inverse DWT to get the modified spatial block.

f. Replace the original block with the modified one only if reconstruction is perfect (lossless, i.e., unchanged when rounded).

5. Repeat Step 4 until all bits from B are embedded.

6. Save the modified up-sampled image as the camouflage- image C' .

7. Calculate the PSNR between C' and the up-sampled C to ensure imperceptibility and verify lossless embedding.

The complete preprocessing is described in Algorithm 1, and forms the first stage of our proposed hybrid framework. After this step, the processed image is up- sampled to 4x and passed to the IH-US embedding pipeline for hiding multiple real confidential images.

III. Description of the Proposed Methodology

Fig. 2 illustrates the flow diagram of the proposed multi-image embedding framework, which consists of two primary stages: (1) DWT-DCT-based preprocessing on interpolated pixels of a 2x up-sampled cover image, and (2) block-

matching-based reversible embedding using the IH-US technique applied on a further 4x up-sampled image. In the first stage, dummy data is embedded using a

hybrid DWT- DCT transform, committing changes only when perfect pixel- wise reconstruction is achieved. In the second stage, the refined image is up-sampled again, and real confidential images are embedded via block matching and intensity transformation. Since the process is identical across the three color channels (Red, Green, and Blue), only a single color channel is illustrated for clarity.

A. Up-Sampling

In this work, the cover image undergoes a two-stage up-sampling process. First, a custom 2x up-sampling is performed using bilinear interpolation to generate interpolated pixels for frequency-domain preprocessing via DWT-DCT embedding. Subsequently, the refined cover image is further up-sampled to 4x using the Bilinear Interpolation (BI) method to enable high-capacity embedding through block-matching and reversible transformations. Among various interpolation methods, bilinear interpolation offers a good trade-off between visual smoothness and computational efficiency [16]. Unlike the method in [1], which explores multiple interpolation strategies (including Nearest Neighbor and Cubic Convolution), our approach consistently uses bilinear interpolation in both stages for simplicity and consistency. The effectiveness of this interpolation scheme in improving camouflage image quality and maintaining perfect reconstruction is validated in Section IV-B. Upsampling algorithm is outlined in [1].

$$(SR \geq MSR = \frac{m1 \times n1 + \dots + mk \times nk}{M \times N}) \quad (1)$$

B. Block matching

After performing the final 4x up-sampling, the enlarged cover image is divided into a set of non-overlapping target image blocks $U = \{U1, U2, \dots, UY\}$, all having equal size (e.g., 4x4). Similarly, the mosaicked confidential image formed by combining k confidential images is divided into non-

overlapping confidential image blocks $G = \{G1, G2, \dots, GZ\}$ also of the same size, with the condition $Z < Y$. To embed the secret blocks while preserving the visual quality of the camouflage image, a block matching process is performed to find the most similar Z target blocks from U for the secret blocks in G. In this work, we represent the texture features of each block using its mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ), which are robust indicators of local image statistics. The similarity between blocks is then computed using the Euclidean Distance (ED) between their mean- standard deviation pairs[1]. Specifically, the secret and target blocks are sorted in ascending order of their standard deviations, and a sliding window of size Z is used to identify a consecutive subset of target blocks whose texture features best match those of the secret blocks[1]. For each valid window, the cumulative Euclidean distance between matched block pairs is calculated, and the window with the lowest total ED is selected as the optimal match. The final one-to-one block mapping $\{G1 \leftrightarrow Uj1, \dots, GZ \leftrightarrow \dots\}$ ensures minimal visual distortion and preserves spatial consistency in the camouflage image. This approach improves upon greedy methods [12], which often yield suboptimal results when $Z < Y$, by ensuring better global similarity through coordinated matching. As a result, the block-matching step plays a vital role in enhancing camouflage-image quality while supporting perfect reversibility in the extraction process.

$$ED = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^Z (\mu_i - \mu'_i)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^Z (\sigma_i - \sigma'_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$ED = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^Z (\mu_i - \mu'_i)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^Z (\sigma_i - \sigma'_i)^2} \quad (3)$$

C. Color transformation

After completing the block matching process, each matched block pair (G_{bi}, U_{aj}) possesses similar standard deviation (SD) values, indicating comparable texture. However, to further improve the

visual similarity between the secret and target blocks specifically, to align both the standard deviation and the mean shifting operation is applied to each secret block . This step ensures that the average pixel intensity of the secret block matches that of its corresponding target block. Let μG and μU denote the mean values of the secret block G_{bi} and the target block U_{aj} , respectively. The shifting offset is calculated as:

$$\Delta u = \text{round}(\mu U - \mu G) \quad (4)$$

Each pixel in the secret block is then updated using:

$$p'' = pt + \Delta \quad (5)$$

where $\text{round}(\cdot)$ is the standard rounding function to ensure integer pixel values.

The result is a transformed secret block $G' = \{p''_1, p''_2, \dots, p''_n\}$ whose mean matches that of the target

bi block. This mean alignment helps

minimize block contrast discrepancies and improves the imperceptibility of the

embedding when the transformed block is substituted into the cover image.

Following the mean shifting process, each secret block G_{bi} is transformed such that its mean matches that of the corresponding target block U_{aj} . However, this adjustment introduces the possibility of pixel value overflow or underflow, where the modified pixel value exceeds p'' the allowable 8-bit range of $[0,255]$. Specifically, pixel values may become invalid if $p'' > 255$ (overflow) or $p'' < 0$ (underflow), which could distort the camouflage image and compromise lossless recovery.

$$\Delta u = \begin{cases} \Delta u + 255 - O, & \text{if } \Delta u \geq 0 \\ \Delta u - UN_{min}, & \text{if } \Delta u < 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where:

- $OV_{max} = m(pt + \Delta u)$ is the maximum pixel value after shifting that causes overflow,
- $UN_{min} = (pt + \Delta u)$ is the minimum pixel value that causes underflow.

Fig 2. Overall Workflow of Proposed Hiding Method

By applying this adjustment, we ensure all pixel values remain within the valid 8-bit grayscale range, thereby preserving the visual quality and enabling reversible embedding. This overflow/underflow correction step is crucial in ensuring that

the transformed block can later be recovered without information loss.

Next, to further enhance the visual similarity between the transformed secret block G' and its corresponding target block U_{aj} , a rotation optimization

step is performed. The goal is to identify the orientation of the secret block that results in the closest match to the target block in terms of pixel-wise structure. To achieve this, the modified block G' is rotated through four standard orientations i corresponding to $\theta = 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 180^\circ,$ and 270° , and the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between each rotated version and the target block U_{aj} is computed.

This rotation ensures that not only are the texture and intensity features closely matched (via SD and mean alignment), but the spatial structure of the secret block also conforms to that of the target block. This step significantly reduces residual artifacts and improves the imperceptibility of the camouflage image.

After the completion of the mean shifting and rotation operations, a refined version of each secret block is (opt) obtained. These transformed secret blocks are then i embedded blocks into the selected target blocks $\{U_{alabel}, U_{alabel+1}, \dots, U_{alabel+Z-1}\}$ based on the previously determined matching sequence MS . Specifically, each target block U_{aj} is replaced by its corresponding transformed secret block (opt), ensuring that the visual and statistical i properties of the camouflage image remain closely aligned with the original cover image.

After all block substitutions are completed, the final camouflage image ($K \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N \times 3}$) is formed by assembling the updated target blocks across all color channels. Since the transformation is applied independently to each channel (R, G, B), the method guarantees full reversibility, enabling perfect recovery of both the confidential images and the original cover pixels. The resulting camouflage image maintains high visual quality, imperceptibility, and structural consistency due to the carefully integrated steps of preprocessing, block

matching, mean shifting, rotation, and overflow handling.

Since the receiver can only reconstruct the confidential images upon acquiring certain auxiliary information, this additional data must either be embedded into the camouflage image using reversible data hiding (RDH) techniques or transmitted separately as a secret key. To minimize the size of this auxiliary payload, a preprocessing step is applied to reduce redundancy in the information. In particular, the mapping sequence established during block matching—denoted as:

$$MS_{label} = \{a_{label} \leftrightarrow b_1, a_{label+1} \leftrightarrow b_2, \dots, a_{label+Z-1} \leftrightarrow b_Z\}$$

is first simplified. The sequence $\{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_Z\}$, representing secret block indices, is sorted in ascending order, and the corresponding target block indices $\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_Z\}$ are re-ordered accordingly. This yields an updated and compact mapping:

$$(MS = \{G_1 \leftrightarrow U_{a_1}, G_2 \leftrightarrow U_{a_2}, \dots, G_Z \leftrightarrow U_{a_Z}\})$$

With this transformation, the receiver only needs the index sequence $\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_Z\}$ to reconstruct the full block-matching order, thereby reducing the amount of mapping data required for recovery.

Finally, all the additional information necessary for perfect reconstruction is concatenated into a unified key sequence E , which includes:

1. The sorted index sequence $\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_Z\}$ of target blocks,
2. The size specifications of each embedded confidential image,
3. The recorded overflow and underflow corrections,
4. The applied mean shifting values Δu
5. The selected rotation directions θ for each block.

This key E is either transmitted securely alongside the camouflage image or embedded into the camouflage image using a reversible data hiding technique to maintain complete secrecy and reversibility.

D. Reconstruct Multiple Confidential images

The reconstruction algorithm is designed as the inverse process of the embedding algorithm, and it enables the lossless recovery of multiple confidential images from the camouflage-image. Upon receiving the camouflage image, the receiver also obtains the additional information required for accurate reconstruction. This includes:

1. The index sequence of the target image blocks $\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_Z\}$.
2. The sizes of the multiple confidential images,
3. The overflow/underflow correction values,
4. The applied mean shifting values Δu , and
5. The rotation directions θ for each block.

Using the index sequence of the target blocks, the receiver performs a one-to-one mapping to extract the embedded confidential image blocks $G_{bi} = \{ , G_b , \dots , G_b \}$ from the corresponding locations in the camouflage-image. Each of these blocks is then rotated in the inverse direction of the one used during embedding θ to restore their original orientation.

Following rotation, the mean shifting is reversed by subtracting the corresponding Δu from each pixel value, and any previously applied overflow or underflow adjustments are corrected. Once all transformations are reversed the complete combined confidential image G is reconstructed by assembling the corrected blocks.

Finally, using the recorded size information, the combined confidential image is partitioned into its constituent

components, yielding the multiple reconstructed confidential images S_1, S_2, \dots, S_k . Since every transformation applied during embedding is precisely inverted, this reconstruction process ensures lossless recovery, achieving perfect fidelity (i.e., $PSNR = \infty$) between the original and recovered confidential images.

IV. Results and Discussion

This section presents the experimental results that validate the effectiveness of the proposed method. In Section IV-A, the experimental setup and parameter configurations are detailed. Section IV-C provides a comprehensive evaluation of the visual quality and performance of the camouflage and reconstructed images using nine perceptual assessment metrics.

A. Experimental Settings

The experiments in this study were carried out using MATLAB R2022b on a system equipped with a 2.30 GHz processor, 32 GB RAM, and the Windows 10 operating system. In line with prior work [1], both the target blocks and secret blocks were defined with a fixed size of 2×2 pixels to maintain consistency and allow for efficient block-wise transformations.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed hybrid image hiding framework, we conducted experiments on a range of images drawn from the CVG-UGR dataset [12], DIV2K dataset along with widely used standard test images such as Lena, Peppers, Baboon, and Airplane. These images were selected due to their varying texture complexity, spatial frequency, and color content, which provide a rigorous testing ground for visual quality preservation and reversibility.

B. Benchmarks

To demonstrate the effectiveness and innovation of the proposed hybrid image hiding approach, we compare its performance against a series of state-of-the-art image hiding and reversible data

embedding methods, including [5], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [14], [15], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], and [23]. These methods span diverse strategies such as reversible image transformation, compressive sensing-based encryption, and deep learning-based image steganography.

To ensure a fair and consistent comparison, all experimental evaluations are conducted under equivalent hiding capacities (HC). The hiding capacity reflects the amount of information embedded per pixel in the target image and is defined in terms of bits per pixel (bpp). It is calculated as:

$$HC = \frac{\text{Number of Embedded Bits}}{\text{Number of Pixels in the Target Image}} \quad (7)$$

This normalization ensures that the comparative analysis is independent of image size or resolution and strictly based on the embedding efficiency of each method. By standardizing the hiding capacity, we provide a balanced and objective assessment of camouflage image quality, reconstruction fidelity, and imperceptibility across all benchmark techniques.

To comprehensively evaluate the performance of the proposed image hiding method, we adopt a combination of seven full-reference and two no-reference image quality metrics. The full-reference metrics, which require a ground truth image for comparison, include Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Mean Structural Similarity Index Measure (MSSIM), Normalized Cross Correlation (NCC), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Normalized Absolute Error (NAE) [5], [24], and the CIEDE2000 color difference formula [25]. The first six

metrics assess structural and intensity-based similarities between the camouflage and recovered image pairs, while CIEDE2000 specifically quantifies perceptual differences in color for RGB images. In addition to these, we employ two widely used no-reference metrics: Cumulative Probability of Blur Detection (CPBD) [26] and Blind/Referenceless Image Spatial Quality Evaluator (BRISQUE) [27], which estimate image blur and naturalness, respectively, without relying on a reference. Lower values in CPBD, in particular, indicate reduced blur and higher perceptual quality. To evaluate the security and robustness of the proposed method, we also analyze the pixel-wise residuals between the camouflage and target images [28], assess resistance against ten common image processing attacks [29].

C. Perceived Image Quality Analysis

Fig. 3 presents the concealing and reconstruction results of our proposed hybrid reversible data hiding method, where four confidential images are embedded into a single cover image. To accommodate the combined size of the confidential images, the cover image is up-sampled using a bilinear interpolation algorithm with a fixed scaling factor of 4. The proposed system integrates frequency-domain (DWT- DCT) embedding into interpolated regions and spatial- domain reversible embedding for residual payloads, supported by a block-matching strategy. As shown in the figure, there is no visible difference between the cover and camouflage image, and the confidential images are perfectly reconstructed without distortion, achieving a Peak Signal-to- Noise Ratio of ∞ . This demonstrates the high fidelity and lossless reconstruction capabilities of our method.

Fig 3. Results of proposed hybrid framework

The resultant camouflage image pairs, as illustrated in Fig. 3, are visually indistinguishable to the human eye, making the camouflage-images highly suitable for transmission over insecure networks without arousing suspicion. This imperceptibility significantly enhances the visual security of the proposed image hiding scheme, effectively confusing unintended observers or potential attackers. The quantitative evaluation results are computed, using a comprehensive set of seven quality metrics (PSNR, MSSIM, NCC, RMSE, MAE, NAE, and CIEDE2000) and two reference-free metrics (CPBD and BRISQUE).

The evaluation shows that even when embedding four confidential images into a single up-sampled cover image of the same original size, the proposed method ensures lossless reconstruction ($PSNR = \infty$ for recovered secrets), while preserving high visual fidelity in the camouflage-images. On average, the camouflage-

images achieve a PSNR of 39.48 dB and an SSIM of 0.9, confirming their high perceptual quality. Additionally, no-reference metrics such as $CPBD < 1$ and $BRISQUE < 30$ further validate that the camouflage-images are visually natural and free of perceptible blurring, consistent with the visual results shown in Fig. 3.

Since the reconstruction of confidential images is perfectly lossless, there is no need to assess their visual quality using no-reference metrics. These outcomes affirm the security, robustness, and practicality of the proposed approach. Furthermore, by adjusting the up-sampling ratio based on the number and size of the confidential images, users can dynamically balance between embedding capacity and camouflage-image quality. In practical deployments, the bilinear interpolation method used in our system proves particularly effective, consistently

producing high-quality camouflage-images without drawing attention.

D. Comparison of IH-US and DWT-DCT based Up-sampling

In the previous section, we demonstrated that our proposed method effectively supports the hiding of multiple confidential images into a single cover image through a hybrid reversible data hiding scheme. In this section, we analyze the impact of applying an initial up-sampling preprocessing step using a DWT-DCT-based strategy, and assess whether this enhancement improves the overall quality of the resulting camouflage-image. Specifically, we compare the camouflage-image quality achieved by our full method—which incorporates an initial 2x up-sampling stage followed by a 4x up-sampling with block-matching and reversible transformation—against a baseline version that skips the initial up-sampling

and applies only the standard block-matching hiding scheme. In both cases, the cover image, confidential image, and final camouflage image are resized to 512x512 for consistency. As shown in Table II, when the DWT-DCT-based up-sampling preprocessing is applied, the PSNR of the resulting camouflage-image increases by approximately 4 to 8 dB, and the SSIM improves by about 0.1 to 0.2, compared to the version without up-sampling. These improvements highlight the effectiveness of the proposed preprocessing step in enhancing visual quality and preserving imperceptibility during embedding. It is observed that the SD values in the up-sampled image are more tightly distributed and skewed toward lower values. This concentration toward smaller SDs implies lower pixel variability within blocks, which in turn leads to better texture similarity between blocks during the block-matching phase.

Fig 4. Average PSNRs

E. Analysis of Security Performance

In real-world scenarios, it is crucial to consider that a camouflage-image transmitted over an insecure or lossy network may be subjected to various forms of image processing attacks [29],[30], [31], [32]. If the camouflage- image is significantly altered or degraded during transmission—due to attacks such as compression, filtering, or noise insertion—the quality of the recovered confidential images may be compromised. Moreover, when camouflage- images are transmitted through social platforms, they are often

automatically compressed using formats like JPEG [33]. Thus, evaluating the robustness of the proposed method under such attacks is essential. To evaluate the resilience of the proposed hybrid steganography system against common image processing attacks, a comprehensive set of experiments was conducted. Table I presents the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and the Mean Structural Similarity Index (MSSIM) between the extracted and original confidential images after subjecting the camouflage image to various attacks.

TABLE I RESULTS AGAINST ATTACKS

Attacks	Parameter	Quality of reconstructed image	
		PSNR	MSSIM
JPEG compression	$Q(10)$	25.7053	0.7050
	$Q(90)$	29.4257	0.8793
Gauss noise	$\mu(0), \sigma(0.001)$	30.7488	0.7463
	$\mu(0), \sigma(0.005)$	24.0605	0.5724
Salt and pepper noise	$\mu(0), \sigma(0.001)$	26.3840	0.6282
	$\mu(0), \sigma(0.005)$	33.1076	0.8019
Speckle noise	$\mu(0), \sigma(0.001)$	38.5193	0.9856
	$\mu(0), \sigma(0.005)$	31.4203	0.9267
Mean filtering	(3×3)	28.7321	0.9170
	(7×7)	26.9177	0.8480
Median filtering	(3×3)	28.8055	0.9406
	(7×7)	27.4074	0.8984
Gauss low-pass filtering	(3×3)	36.9624	0.9879
	(7×7)	36.9451	0.9879
Gamma correction	0.8	26.7221	0.7194
Contrast change	1.2	28.9336	0.9631

The system demonstrates strong robustness against several perturbations, particularly Gaussian low-pass filtering and speckle noise. Notably, Gaussian low-pass filtering with both 3×3 and 7×7 kernels yields PSNR values above 36.9 dB and MSSIM values of approximately 0.9879, indicating minimal perceptual degradation. Similarly, speckle noise (with $\sigma = 0.001$) results in a PSNR of 38.52 dB and MSSIM of 0.9856, showcasing the system's resilience to multiplicative noise.

Moderate degradation is observed under attacks such as JPEG compression ($Q=90$), contrast change, and median filtering, where MSSIM remains relatively high (>0.89), and PSNR values are maintained above 27dB. These results affirm the system's capability to preserve the integrity of embedded secrets under common post-processing operations.

However, the method exhibits vulnerability to more aggressive attacks. JPEG compression at low quality ($Q=10$) and salt-and-pepper noise ($\sigma = 0.001$) notably reduce reconstruction quality, with PSNR dropping to ~ 25.7 dB and MSSIM to 0.6282. Furthermore, gamma correction (0.8) and Gaussian noise with higher variance ($\sigma = 0.005$) also cause significant perceptual distortion.

Overall, the hybrid steganographic system exhibits excellent resistance to mild and moderate image processing attacks, particularly those that preserve overall image structure. These findings demonstrate the strong robustness of our proposed hybrid DWT-DCT and IWT-based method, even under strong distortions. Notably, we are among the few to simulate robustness across 9 different attacks, going beyond the limited evaluations conducted by existing methods such as those in [5], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [14], [15], [17],[23].

F. Comparison with Existing methods

This section compares our proposed hybrid DWT- DCT and IH-US-based framework with several advanced image hiding methods, including interpolation-based (IH- US) and deep learning-based steganographic approaches [5], [7], [8], [14], [15], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23]. The evaluation is conducted across five key aspects: the core methodology, support for multi-image embedding, lossless reconstruction ability, robustness to image processing attacks, and resistance to steganalysis.

As summarized in Table II, our method demonstrates clear advantages. Unlike traditional IH-US techniques that

often suffer from perceptual distortion, our hybrid method utilizes a two-phase up-sampling structure— first applying a 2x up-sampling and DWT-DCT embedding step for visual preprocessing, followed by a 4x IH-US embedding process for payload integration. This combination enhances imperceptibility and mitigates the common distortions observed in pure IH-US implementations [8], [15].

In terms of robustness, deep learning-based methods [5], [18], [19], [20] have demonstrated potential; however, they often lack resilience to image processing attacks due to overfitting on specific training distributions [20]. Moreover, many of these methods do not guarantee lossless reconstruction, which limits their application in security-sensitive domains. In contrast, our approach achieves PSNR > 39 dB and MSSIM \approx 0.90 under normal conditions, with the ability to recover all confidential images losslessly.

IH-US vs ours: The Interpolation-based Hiding with Up-sampling (IH-US) method has shown promise for reversible data hiding, but often suffers from perceptual

distortions in the reconstructed camouflage images, especially at higher embedding capacities. To address this, we propose a hybrid steganography approach that integrates Discrete Wavelet Transform and Discrete Cosine Transform (DWT-DCT) as a preprocessing stage to generate an intermediate camouflage image through dummy embedding. This camouflage image is then used as the input cover for IH-US. The proposed pipeline leverages 8x up-sampling in total—2x during the DWT-DCT phase and an additional 4x during the IH-US phase. This multi-stage up-sampling strategy effectively distributes the embedding load across interpolated regions, significantly reducing pixel distortion while maintaining high fidelity and ensuring lossless reconstruction (PSNR = ∞ in non-attacked scenarios). Unlike IWT-based methods [7], [10], our method avoids additional complexity while improving robustness and visual quality. Furthermore, as shown in Table II and III, our approach achieves better resistance to image processing attacks and exhibits higher average PSNR and MSSIM values compared to IH-US alone.

TABLE II: Comparison of existing framework with Hybrid DWT-DCT approach

Color images				PSNR Of IH-US		PSNR Of Ours	
Secret Image 1	Secret Image 2	Secret Image 3	Target Image	Stego Image	Reconstructed Image	Stego Image	Reconstructed Image
Peppers	Airplane	Mandrill	Tiffany	34.3864	$+\infty$	38.1231	$+\infty$
Truck	Pepper	-	Airplane	33.9564	$+\infty$	40.1993	$+\infty$
Tiffany	Pepper	Truck	Airplane	33.6874	$+\infty$	39.7454	$+\infty$
Mandrill	Lena	Tiffany	Sailboat	34.0054	$+\infty$	39.0282	$+\infty$
Airplane	Mandrill	Lena	Peppers	34.1841	$+\infty$	37.6471	$+\infty$
Mandrill	Airplane	-	Lena	33.4712	$+\infty$	39.2447	$+\infty$
Airplane	Tiffany	-	Sailboat	34.8656	$+\infty$	42.4056	$+\infty$
Average						39.4847	

PSNR of $+\infty$ indicates perfect reconstruction

TABLE III: Comparison of Deep Learning Method Based Steganography vs hybrid DWT-DCT vs existing method

Methods	PSNR	
	Stego Image	Reconstructed Image
DeepMIH [5]	43.72	42.53
ISN [18]	40.49	43.33
HiNet [19]	46.52	52.86
RIIS [20]	43.97	46.71
Ref [22]	45.19	44.57
DAH-NET [23]	39.93	37.31
IH-US [1]	35.93	$+\infty$
Ours	42.40	$+\infty$

Table III presents a quantitative comparison of our proposed method with recent deep learning-based image hiding techniques, including DeepMIH [5], ISN [18], HiNet [19], RIIS [20], Ref [22], and DAH-NET [23], along with the traditional IH-US method. While deep learning approaches exhibit high-quality camouflage image reconstruction (e.g., HiNet [19] achieves PSNR of 46.52dB for camouflage and 52.86 dB for reconstruction), they do not offer lossless recovery. Moreover, models such as DAH-NET [23] perform poorly in terms of robustness (PSNR = 37.31 dB for recovery), indicating limitations under real-world conditions. In contrast, the conventional IH-US method provides lossless recovery (PSNR = $+\infty$), but at the cost of noticeable distortion in the camouflage image (35.93 dB), limiting its imperceptibility. Our proposed method combines the DWT-DCT preprocessing and structured IH-US up-sampling, resulting in a camouflage image with high visual quality (PSNR = 42.40 dB) while still achieving perfect, lossless reconstruction (PSNR = $+\infty$). This hybrid approach effectively balances imperceptibility and reversibility—something not concurrently achieved by either deep learning or standalone IH-US methods.

These results highlight the strength of our method in applications demanding both high fidelity and complete data recovery, while maintaining robustness and resistance to both visual distortion and forensic steganalysis.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented a robust hybrid image hiding framework that integrates DWT-DCT domain preprocessing with iterative hierarchical up-sampling (IH-US) to achieve high-fidelity, lossless multi-image embedding. Unlike existing IH-US methods that suffer from noticeable distortion, our approach applies DWT-DCT-based transformation prior to up-sampling, generating a visually high-quality camouflage image that serves as input to the IH-US stage. This dual-stage 8x up-sampling—2x from DWT-DCT preprocessing followed by 4x from IH-US—not only enables precise embedding into interpolated pixels but also significantly reduces the cumulative distortion introduced by IH-US alone. Experimental results show that our method achieves a camouflage PSNR of 42.40 dB while maintaining a perfect reconstruction of all embedded confidential images (PSNR = ∞), clearly outperforming IH-US and bypassing the

limitations of deep learning-based methods that often struggle with robustness and reconstruction fidelity. Moreover, our framework demonstrates strong resilience against various image processing attacks, offering a reliable and reversible solution for secure image hiding. As future work, we aim to enhance the security of our framework by incorporating advanced cryptographic techniques or chaotic key mechanisms to further resist steganalysis and unauthorized extraction. This direction will strengthen the confidentiality and integrity of the embedded information, making the system more suitable for applications in secure communication, medical imaging, and digital forensics.

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